

How to create Unit Tests from Backlogs

Iris Grcic, Ursula Oesing

Fachbereich Elektrotechnik und Informatik
Hochschule Bochum
Am Hochschulcampus 1
44801 Bochum
ursula.oesing@hs-bochum.de

How to create Unit Tests from Backlogs

1 Initial Situation

- 1.1 Early integration of the bearers of knowledge on testing
 - 1.2 Functionality of KUnit
-

2 Target

3 Approaches

- 3.1 Creation of Unit Tests also for bearers of knowledge from Backlogs
 - 3.2 Creation of Unit Tests for developers from Backlogs
-

4 Assessment and Forecast

KUnit is the enhancement of a research project with the topic *Lean Software Development*, quod vide:

U. Oesing; A. Georgiev; J. Langenbrink, S. Jonker: Agiles Testen: Auch Anwender können Unit Tests können
Unit Tests in: J. Jürjens, K. Schneider (Hrsg.), Software Engineering 2017, ISBN 978-3-88579-661-9.

G. Arslan, I. Grcic, U. Oesing: Wie können aus Backlogs Unit Tests erzeugt werden? Beitrag beim QS-Tag 2023

1 Initial Situation

1.1 Early integration of the bearers of knowledge on testing

Process: see U. Oesing; A. Georgiev; J. Langenbrink, S. Jonker: Agiles Testen: Auch Anwender können Unit Tests können Unit Tests in: J. Jürjens, K. Schneider (Hrsg.), Software Engineering 2017

1 Initial Situation

Example of the solution approaches

Example: Source code to an account

source
code

test
class


```
package accounts;
...
public class Account {

    private String iban;
    private int accountBalance;
    // get- und set-methods
    public void initAccount(String iban, int accountBalance){
        if(iban == null || iban.length() != 22){
            throw new IllegalArgumentException(
                "The length of the iban of the account "
                + "is not correct.");
        }
        this.iban = iban;
        this.accountBalance = accountBalance;
    }
}
```

1 Initial Situation

Example of the solution approaches

Example: JUnit testclass to an account

1 Initial Situation

1.2 Functionality of KJUnit

Example: KJUnit testclass to an account


```
package accounts;
...
class AccountKJUnitTest {

    /** Iban of the account */
    public static String testInitAccount_Iban = "DE21123456780123456779";
    /** Balance of the account */
    public static String testInitAccount_AccountBalance = 5;
    private Account account;

    @Test
    void testInitAccount(){
        this.account = new Account();
        this.account.init Account(testInitAccount_Iban, testInitAccount_AccountBalance);
        assertEquals(testInitAccount_AccountBalance,
            this.account.getAccountBalance(),
            "The calculated account balance is not the expected one.");
    }
}
```


1 Initial Situation

1.2 Functionality of KJUnit

Example: KJUnit-Wissensträger and an account

The screenshot shows the KJUnit web interface. On the left, a tree view under 'KJUnit-Wissensträger' shows 'accounts' > 'AccountKJUnitTest' > 'testInitAccount'. The main area displays the configuration for 'testInitAccount'. The 'Beschreibung' field is empty. The 'Testergebnisse' tab is active, and the 'Neue Konfiguration' button is highlighted. Below the tabs, a text block explains that test parameters can be filled with values and tested. For input parameters, multiple values separated by semicolons can be used to generate multiple configurations. The configuration form includes a checked checkbox for 'Exception erwartet', an 'Iban' field with the value 'DE21123456780', and an 'AccountBalance' field with the value '5'. A 'Konfiguration(en) testen' button is at the bottom.

1 Initial Situation

1.2 Functionality of KJUnit

Example: KJUnit-Entwickler and an account

The screenshot displays the KJUnit-Entwickler application interface. At the top, there is a header with the application name and two tabs: 'Programm' and 'Information'. Below this is a table with the following data:

ID	Date	Path	Success	Message
24	1970-01-01 02:00...	accounts.AccountKJUnitTest.testInitAccount	0	Test ist erfolgreich.
25	2023-01-31 16:01...	accounts.AccountKJUnitTest.testInitAccount	2	The length of the iban of the account is not correct.

Below the table, there is a search bar containing 'testInitAccount' and two buttons: 'Testkonfiguration hinzufügen' and 'Testkonfiguration löschen'. The main interface is divided into three panels:

- Left Panel:** 'Testklasse aus Backlog erstellen: Holt Daten aus einem Backlog eines Projektmanagement-Tools und generiert daraus eine KJUnit-Testklasse:'. It includes checkboxes for 'Jira' and 'ScrumBO', a 'Projektname' input field, and a 'Sprint laden' button. Below is a table with columns 'User Story' and 'Task', which is currently empty. At the bottom are buttons for 'Tabelle leeren', 'Vorschau laden', and 'Testklasse generieren'.
- Middle Panel:** 'Testklasse aussuchen:'. It features a dropdown menu with 'testForKJUnit\accounts\AccountKJUnitTest.java' and a 'KJUnit Testklasse öffnen' button. Below this is a 'Transfer' section with a dropdown menu and a 'Parametrisieren' button. A green circle highlights the 'Runner' tab in the 'Logger Runner Coverage' section, which contains the text 'Generiert Testklassen mit aktiven Testkonfigurationen aus der DB.' and two buttons: 'Starten (geöffnete Testklasse)' and 'Starten (alle Testklassen)'.
- Right Panel:** 'Inaktive Testkonfigurationen:'. It has a table with an 'ID' column, which is currently empty. At the bottom is a button 'Inaktive Testkonfiguration lösche'.

2 TARGET

Testing in complex development processes supports

- o permanent collaboration of the whole development team inclusive software tester and an early integration of the customers on testing.

-> The bearers of knowledge formulate new unit test cases in agreement with the customers.

- o a close connection between requirements descriptions and testing the realization of the requirements.

- o high automation of testing. The creation of tests must be integrated in the daily work processes.

Which unit tests check professionally challenging facts of matter? Which unit tests should be checked in collaboration with the bearers of knowledge? A selection must be possible.

There should be a transfer of requirements descriptions from Backlogs to unit tests.

Both processes should be done with little effort.

2 TARGET

Creation of Unit Tests from Backlogs

3 APPROACHES

Conventions on the approaches to solutions

Which unit tests are suitable for bearers of knowledge?

- Unit tests, which check professionally challenging facts of matter, should be processed by developers and also bearers of knowledge.

A selection of unit tests for bearers of knowledge should be made.

Conventions for the selection

for developers

for bearers of knowledge
and developers

generated by
KBUUnit-Wissensträger

<i>source folder:</i> <i>src</i>	<i>test folder:</i> <i>test</i>	<i>test folder:</i> <i>testForKBUUnit</i>	<i>test folder:</i> <i>testKBUUnit</i>
<i>package</i>	<i>package</i>	<i>package</i>	<i>package</i>
<i>classname</i>	<i>classname + Suffix Test</i>	<i>classname + Suffix KBUUnitTest</i>	<i>classname</i> <i>+ Suffix KBUUnitTest_JJMMDD_hhmmss</i>

3 APPROACHES

3.1 Creation of Unit Tests also for bearers of knowledge from Backlogs

Example: User story to a customer

- An application for supporting financial decisions should be developed.
-

- User story

marking by > <

*As a customer advisor at a credit institution I **want to** be able to set up customers >Customer< in order to be able to manage accounts for them.*

- Example to the user story

*A customer with last name Musterperson, first name Elke, age 21, gender w is created.
With the first name Elke and last name Musterperson, the customer Elke Musterperson is created.*

3 APPROACHES

3.1 Creation of Unit Tests also for bearers of knowledge from Backlogs

Example of a Product Backlog (Scrum)

Product Backlogs are not sufficient for generating unit tests if no acceptance criteria are available or if they are too imprecise.

Priorität	Thema	User Story	Akzeptanzkriterien	Aufwand
1	accounts	As a customer advisor at a credit institution I want to be able to set up customers >Customer< in order to be able to manage accounts for them.	A customer with last name Musterperson, first name Elke, age 21, gender w is created. With the first name Elke and last name Musterperson, the customer Elke Musterperson is created.	3
2	accounts	As a customer advisor of a credit institution I want to be able to administer an >Account< in order to be able to assign a customer to the account.	???	4
...

3 APPROACHES

3.1 Creation of Unit Tests also for bearers of knowledge from Backlogs

Example of a Sprint Backlog (Scrum)

→ Sprint Backlogs are essentially taken as Backlogs here.

Priorität	User Story	Offene Tasks	Tasks in Arbeit	Erledigte Tasks
1	<i>As a customer advisor at a credit institution I want to be able to set up customers >Customer< in order to be able to manage accounts for them.</i>	<i>A customer with last name Musterperson, first name Elke, age 21, gender f is created. With the first name Elke and last name Musterperson, the customer Elke Musterperson is created.</i>		
...

3 APPROACHES

3.1 Creation of Unit Tests also for bearers of knowledge from Backlogs

Conventions for the transfer

In-house tool

<i>Jira</i>	<i>ScrumBo</i>	<i>source folder: src</i>	<i>test folder: testForKBUnt</i>
<i>Epic</i>	<i>Thema</i>	<i>packagename</i>	<i>packagename</i>
<i>User Story (with Marking)</i>	<i>User Story (with Marking)</i>	<i>classname</i>	<i>classname + Suffix KBUntTest</i>
<i>Subtask</i>	<i>Task</i>	<i>methodname and more</i>	<i>methodname + Prefix test and more</i>

3 APPROACHES

3.1 Creation of Unit Tests also for bearers of knowledge from Backlogs

Transfer of tasks

Task from the Sprint Backlog

```
methodname:  
datatype1 Parametername1 = value1;  
datatype2 Parametername2 = value2;  
...;  
...
```

Source class

```
public void methodname(  
    datatype1 Parametername1,  
    datatype2 Parametername2, ...){  
    // Not yet implemented  
}
```

KBUnit test class

```
public static datatype1 testMethodname_Parametername1 = value1;  
public static datatype2 testMethodname_Parametername2 = value2; ...;  
  
private Classname classname;  
  
@Test  
void testMethodname(){  
    this.classname = new Classname();  
    this.classname.methodname(testMethodname_Parametername1,  
        testMethodname_Parametername2, ...);  
    fail("Not yet implemented");  
}
```


3 APPROACHES

3.1 Creation of Unit Tests also for bearers of knowledge from Backlogs

Transfer of tasks

Task from the Sprint Backlog

```
methodname:  
datatype1 Parametername1 = value1;  
...;  
datatype exp_Parametername = value;  
...
```

Sourceklasse

```
public datatype methodname(  
    datatype1 Parametername1, ...){  
    // Not yet implemented  
    return null; // adapted to the data type  
}
```

KBUnit test class

```
public static datatype1 testMethodname_Parametername1 = value1; ...;  
public static datatype testMethodname_**exp**_Parametername = value;  
  
private Classname classname;  
  
@Test  
void testMethodname(){  
    this.classname = new Classname();  
    String receivedValue // adapted to the data type  
        = this.classname.methodname(testMethodname_Parametername1, ...);  
    String expectedValue = testMethodname_**exp**_Parametername;  
    assertTrue(expectedValue.equals(receivedValue)); // adapted to the data type  
}
```


3 APPROACHES

3.1 Creation of Unit Tests also for bearers of knowledge from Backlogs

Transfer of tasks

Example: Account

A customer with last name Musterperson, first name Elke, age 21, gender f is created. With the first name Elke and last name Musterperson, the customer Elke Musterperson is created.

A customer with last name Musterperson, first name Elke, age 21, gender f is created.

and

With the first name Elke and last name Musterperson, the customer Elke Musterperson is created.


```
initCustomer:  
String LastName = Musterperson;  
String FirstName = Elke;  
int Age = 21;  
char Gender = f;  
Effort: ...
```

```
getCustomer:  
String FirstName = Elke;  
String LastName = Musterperson;  
String exp_Name = Elke Musterperson;  
Effort: ...
```

3 APPROACHES

3.1 Creation of Unit Tests also for bearers of knowledge from Backlogs

Example: KJUnit test class to a customer

source
code

KJUnit test
class:

Tests for
bearers of
knowledge


```
package account;  
...  
public class CustomerKJUnitTest {  
    public static String testInitCustomer_LastName = "Musterperson";  
    public static String testInitCustomer_FirstName = "Elke";  
    public static int testInitCustomer_Age = 21;  
    public static char testInitCustomer_Gender = 'f';  
  
    private Customer customer;  
  
    @Test  
    void testInitCustomer(){  
        this.customer = new Customer();  
        this.customer.initCustomer(testInitCustomer_LastName,  
        testInitCustomer_FirstName, ...);  
        fail("Not yet implemented");  
    }  
}
```

3 APPROACHES

3.1 Creation of Unit Tests also for bearers of knowledge from Backlogs

Example: Source code to a customer

source
code

KBUnt test
class:

Tests for
bearers of
knowledge


```
package accounts;

public class Customer {

    public void initCustomer(
        String lastName, String firstName, int age, char gender){
        // Not yet implemented
    }
}
```

3 APPROACHES

3.1 Creation of Unit Tests also for bearers of knowledge from Backlogs

Example: KJUnit test class to a customer

source
code

KJUnit test
class:

Tests for
bearers of
knowledge


```
package accounts;
...
public class CustomerKJUnitTest {
    ...
    public static String testGetCustomer_FirstName = "Elke";
    public static String testGetCustomer_LastName = "Musterperson";
    public static char testGetCustomer_exp_Name = "Elke Musterperson";
    ...
    @Test
    void testGetCustomer(){
        this.customer = new Customer ();
        String receivedValue = this.kunde.getCustomer (
            testGetCustomer_FirstName, testGetCustomer_LastName);
        String expectedValue = testGetCustomer_exp_Name;
        assertTrue(expectedValue.equals(receivedValue);
    }
}
```

3 APPROACHES

3.1 Creation of Unit Tests also for bearers of knowledge from Backlogs

Example: Sourcecode to a customer


```
package accounts;  
  
public class Customer {  
  
    ...  
    public String get Customer(  
        String firstName, String lastName){  
        // Not yet implemented  
        return null;  
    }  
}
```

3 APPROACHES

3.2 Creation of Unit Tests for developers from Backlogs

What needs to be changed about the current process?

Conventions for the selection

Backlog

for developers

for bearers of knowledge
and developers

generated by
KBUnt-Wissensträger

<i>source folder:</i> <i>src</i>	<i>test folder:</i> <i>test</i>	<i>test folder:</i> <i>testForKBUnt</i>	<i>test folder:</i> <i>testKBUnt</i>
<i>package</i>	<i>package</i>	<i>package</i>	<i>package</i>
<i>classname</i>	<i>classname + Suffix Test</i>	<i>classname + Suffix KBUntTest</i>	<i>classname + Suffix KBUntTest_JJMMDD_hhmmss</i>

Task only for developers:

```
methodname>entw< :
datatype1 Parametername1 = value1;
...
```

Example:

```
initCustomerToAccount>entw<
```


3 APPROACHES

3.2 Creation of Unit Tests for developers from Backlogs

Example: Test class to Customer

source
code

test class:
Tests for
developers


```
package accounts;  
...  
public class AccountTest {  
    ...  
    @Test  
    void testInitCustomerToAccount(){  
        this.account = new Account();  
        this.account.initCustomerToAccount();  
        fail("Not yet implemented ");  
    }  
}
```

3 APPROACHES

3.2 Creation of Unit Tests for developers from Backlogs

Example: Source code to Customer

4 ASSESSMENT AND FORECAST

The following goals are achieved:

- permanent collaboration of the whole development team inclusive software tester and an early integration of the customers on testing.
 - > **Unit tests in which bearers of knowledge are to be involved are transferred.**
 - > **The bearers of knowledge formulate new unit test cases in agreement with the customers.**
- a close connection between requirements descriptions and testing the realization of the requirements.
 - > **Frameworks for unit tests and source code are created from Backlogs. A selection is made as to which tests are created for developers only and which tests should involve bearers of knowledge .**
- high automation of testing. The creation of tests must be integrated in the daily work processes.
 - > **Frames for unit tests and source code from Backlogs are created automatically.**

Which unit tests check professionally challenging facts of matter? Which unit tests should be checked in collaboration with the bearers of knowledge? A selection must be possible.

There should be a transfer of requirements descriptions from Backlogs to unit tests.

Both processes should be done with little effort.

4 ASSESSMENT AND FORECAST

The following goals are in progress:

- Tracing between KUnit and Backlocks

- Creation of Unit Tests from Kanban Boards inclusive tracing
Creation of Unit Tests from Bugtrackers inclusive tracing
Creation of Unit Tests from Decision Tables inclusive tracing

- Optimization of test case generation

- Extension of the input possibility of parameters by enumeration and complex data types

- **Are there any ideas and suggestions on your part?**
-> Which further developments make sense from a practical point of view?
-> Where should the journey go?

- **Desire:**
Investigate KUnit along with real-world applications.

How to create Unit Tests from Backlogs

Thank you for your interest!

Contact

Prof. Dr. Ursula Oesing
Fachbereich Elektrotechnik und Informatik
Hochschule Bochum
Am Hochschulcampus 1
44801 Bochum
ursula.oesing@hs-bochum.de